

Chelate Formation of Penicillins with Certain Tervalent Carcinogenic Metal Ions

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Chelate formation of the two most common and widely used penicillins (penicillin-G and penicillin-V) has been studied with some trivalent carcinogenic metal ions e.g. Fe(III), Al(III) and Cr(III) using Calvin-Bjerrum's pH-titration technique as adopted by Irving and Rossotti in 50% aqueous-acetone solution at 30° and in 0.1M ionic strength (NaClO₄). The stepwise formation constants indicate the order of stability to vary as : Al(III) < Fe(III) < Cr(III). The maximum value of \bar{n} reaches ~2 in every case, indicating formation of ML and ML₂ complexes only. This suggests that two coordination positions remain unoccupied with the expected octahedral geometry of the complexes, which may be utilised for combination with tissues.

CANCER formation and its inhibition both involve chelation. Carcinogenic metals are generally transition metals, which have pronounced tendency for chelation and are associated with vitamins, proteins and nucleic acids. In our earlier communications we reported chelate formation of these penicillins with certain bivalent metal ions¹⁻³, in the present communication we report the chelate formation of penicillin-G(PG) and penicillin-V(PV) with some carcinogenic trivalent metal ions e.g. Fe(III), Cr(III) and Al(III) in 50% aqueous acetone solution at 30° and 0.1 M ionic strength with NaClO₄, using Calvin-Bjerrum's pH-titration technique⁴ as adopted by Irving and Rossotti⁵.

Experimental

All the reagents employed were of high purity. The preparation and standardisation of the metal and the ligand solutions and the other experimental details remaining the same as given in the earlier communication¹.

Stoichiometry of the complexes formed was ascertained by potentiometric and conductometric titrations, utilising the monovariation method⁶. For conductometric studies WTW, LBR, Germany, conductivity-bridge, with the dip-type conductivity cell was used. 10 ml. of the ligand solution (0.01 M) was diluted to 100 ml. and was titrated with 0.01 M metal solution. The conductance were recorded after each addition of 0.5 ml. of the metal solution and were corrected to the dilution effect. pH-measurements were done on 'Systronics', pH-meter No. 322 using glass-calomel electrode assembly in conjunction with saturated calomel electrode.

The Bjerrum-Calvin⁴ pH-titration technique as adopted by Irving and Rossotti⁵ was followed to determine various formation constants. For pH

titrations, the following mixtures keeping acetone-water ratio 1 : 1 in 50 ml. of the reaction solutions were titrated against carbonate free 0.2 M KOH :

- (A) 5ml. of 0.04 M HClO₄
- (B) Mixture (A)+10 ml. of 0.02 M Ligand.
- (C) Mixture (B)+5 ml. of 0.002 M metal solution.

The ionic strength of the above solutions was maintained to 0.1 M by adding the required quantity of 0.1 M NaClO₄ solution. Correction for pH-measurements in 50% acetone-water system was done as described by Van-Uitert and Hass⁷ and Irving-Rossotti⁵. On progressive addition of the alkali during the pH-titrations a precipitate was obtained in each case. The pH of preprecipitation in the different systems being : Fe-PG/PV, 5.6 ; Cr-PG/PV, 5.5 ; Al-PG ; 5.2 and Al-PV, 3.8. Therefore, in these cases all the calculations have been done below the pH of preprecipitations. Further, with the use of very dilute solutions (1 × 10⁻⁴ M) of the metals, possibility of the formation of polynuclear complexes may be ruled out.

Metal-Ligand formation constants :

In the stepwise complex formation, the nth metal-ligand stability constant (K_n) is given by—

$$K_n = \frac{CML_n}{CML_{n-1} \cdot CL} \dots\dots\dots (n=1,2,\dots,n)$$

For plotting formation-curves (graph between average number of ligand bound to metal (\bar{n}) and free ligand exponent (pL), \bar{n} and pL values were calculated using the equations :

$$\bar{n} = \frac{(V''' - V'') (N^0 + E^0)}{(V^0 + V') \cdot \bar{n}_A \cdot TCM^0}$$

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$$pL = \log_{10} \left[\frac{\sum_{n=0}^{n_{\text{max}}} \beta_n^H \left(\frac{1}{\text{antilog } B} \right)^n}{\text{TCL}^{\circ} - \bar{n} \cdot \text{TCM}^{\circ}} \cdot \frac{V^{\circ} - V'''}{V^{\circ}} \right]$$

where TCM° is total concentration of metals; B is the pH , β_n^H , overall proton ligand constant and V' , V'' , V''' are the volume of alkali required to reach the same pH in acid, ligand and metal titration curves, while N° and E° are the normality of alkali and strength of acid in 50 ml. of the solution. The values of $\log K_1$, $\log K_2$ and $\log \beta_2$ were recorded directly from the formation curves and refined by the best least-square fits. The refined values are given in Table 1.

TABLE 1—STABILITY CONSTANTS : PENICILLIN COMPLEXES

Metal	$\mu = 0.1M$ (NaClO ₄)		Temp. : 30°C.			
	PG	PV	PG	PV	PG	PV
Al(III)	5.40	4.59	4.70	4.04	10.10	8.63
Fe(III)	5.47	4.80	4.75	4.06	10.23	8.86
Cr(III)	5.50	4.95	4.77	4.48	10.27	9.43

Results and Discussion

The conductometric and pH -titrations and the maximum values of \bar{n} (~ 2) indicate formation of ML and ML₂ complexes in the systems studied.

The tervalent ions studied here include two transitional Cr(III) and Fe(III) and one nontransitional metal Al(III). According to the expectations and transitional metals complexes were found more stable. However, the order obtained for the complexes studied in this investigation does not follow the order suggested earlier by Irving-Williams⁸ and Fernalies *et al*⁹. According to which Fe(III) complexes should have greater stability over that of Cr(III); but the order obtained here varies as; Cr(III) > Fe(III) and follows the order of the second ionisation potential and e^2/r -ratio for the metallic

ions. Thus, the order of stability obtained seems to follow the order of increasing polarisability :

$$P = \frac{Z-S}{r} \text{ where, } P = \text{Proportionality constant}$$

Z =atomic number, S =screening effect constant and r =radii. For the regular octahedral complexes, according to CFT the degenerated d-AO of the metal ion split into two new levels the lower triplet, t_{2g} electrons increases the screening effect in the direction perpendicular to the centres of the faces of the octahedron, hence do not influence the interaction between metal and ligand appreciably. While the number of electrons in eg AOs affect the screening effect linearly, thus, greater is the number of eg-electrons, weaker is the polarising effect and hence the metal to ligand bond. Fe(III) (ad^5) in an octahedral field, will have three electrons in t_{2g} and two electrons in eg-AOs, while Cr(III) $3d^3$ there will be no electron in eg AOs, resulting in the higher stability of its complexes due to polarising action.

Further, the stoichiometry of the complexes indicate formation of only two, ML and ML₂ complexes. This suggests that two coordination positions remain unoccupied with the expected octahedral geometry of the complexes, which may be utilised for combination with tissues.

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